

TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE ASSESSMENT CRITERIA AND ANALYSIS

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Abstract. *This article examines the role of transport infrastructure and logistics performance in ensuring sustainable economic growth. The study analyzes the Logistics Performance Index (LPI) indicators of Central Asian countries, Turkey, and the world for the period 2007–2025. Special attention is given to key LPI components, including customs efficiency, infrastructure quality, international shipments, logistics service quality, cargo tracking, and timeliness of delivery. The results show that Central Asian countries remain below the global average in logistics performance, while Turkey demonstrates comparatively higher indicators due to its developed transport infrastructure and strategic position as a Eurasian transport hub. The analysis also reveals that Uzbekistan and Tajikistan have considerable growth potential, although access to international markets and transport corridors remains a major challenge. The article concludes that modernization, digitalization, investment attraction, and institutional reforms are essential for improving logistics efficiency and strengthening international competitiveness.*

Keywords: *logistics, transport infrastructure, Logistics Performance Index, sustainable economic growth, international trade, digitalization, Central Asia.*

Introduction

Time has transformed global technology, and over more than half a century since the Second World War, the world has witnessed extremely rapid economic development, as well as dynamic and adaptive progress. At the same time, human society has faced serious threats: in industrially developed countries, shortages of resources and infrastructure problems have emerged, while in developing countries, the pressures of population growth and development have intensified. Global economic development inevitably creates serious problems related to its environmental and ecological impact in both industrialized and developing countries. The historical experience of the past fifty years shows that economic growth cannot be achieved without the sustainable use of natural resources, environmental protection and preservation, effective use of time, and ecological awareness. Sustainability is a major economic, ecological, and social challenge for future economic development.

Sustainable economic growth refers to the consistent, balanced, and crisis-free development of an economy over a long period of time. Therefore, internal and external, political-economic, and social problems inevitably affect such a situation. Global challenges, including crises in the world economy such as pandemics, inflation, and geopolitical tensions, have been occurring frequently. Resources are limited, and environmental problems have reached a high level. Social inequalities are also increasing in societies.

Sustainable economic growth is important for the following reasons: ensuring economic stability, including inflation control, unemployment reduction, continuity of economic strategy, and stabilization of the national currency; improving the well-being of the population, including ensuring and increasing income equality, reducing poverty, and improving healthcare and

education; using resources efficiently, including resource conservation, maintaining ecological balance, and reducing the transportation of resources; and creating convenient infrastructure in all sectors.

Literature Review

The issue of the impact of transport infrastructure on economic development has been widely studied in international scientific literature. In most studies, the transport system is regarded as the main driver of economic growth. For example, in his work, D. Aschauer emphasizes that public investment in transport infrastructure is one of the most important factors increasing production productivity. Also, a World Bank report indicates that the development of transport infrastructure is of decisive importance in increasing trade volume, reducing logistics costs, and strengthening regional integration.

If attention is paid to the experience of developed countries, the high level of organization of transport and logistics infrastructure in Germany and Japan serves the stable and regionally balanced development of the economy. In particular, according to OECD data, investments directed to transport networks ensure long-term economic efficiency and stimulate production activity even in remote regions.

In the conditions of Uzbekistan, special attention is also being paid to the development of transport infrastructure. In the “Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026,” the expansion of road and railway networks and the modernization of logistics centers are defined as the main task of strengthening interregional integration. At the same time, local researchers, for example, A. G‘aniev and M. Xasanov, in their scientific works, separately emphasize the importance of transport infrastructure in reducing regional economic disparities.

In conclusion, the literature review shows that the development of transport infrastructure not only accelerates economic growth but is also regarded as an effective means of reducing interregional economic inequality.

The global transport strategy is aimed at decarbonization, sustainability, and connectivity, and it is directed toward reducing greenhouse gases by 2050 through the adoption of electric vehicles, improvement of railways, and efficient infrastructure. The main goals include supporting global trade, introducing multimodal connectivity, strengthening and increasing efficiency, and improving digital solutions to reduce environmental impact.

Methodology

Main components of the global transport strategy:

Decarbonization (Net-Zero Goals): The main focus is on the transition to electric vehicles and low-carbon fuel by 2030, with the aim of electric engines occupying 35% of the global market by 2030.

Infrastructure and connectivity: This includes the development of networks such as expanding high-speed rail, improving port capacity, and increasing freight transport efficiency.

Sustainable urban mobility: Developing public transport, pedestrian, and bicycle infrastructure in order to create healthy cities and reduce dependence on private, high-emission vehicles.

Technological innovations: Integrating intelligent transport systems (ITS) and digital logistics tools to optimize route planning and reduce transportation time.

Private sector involvement: Encouraging private investment in new technologies, infrastructure, and operational efficiency in order to develop reforms and innovations.

Main regional and global initiatives:

The United Nations Decade of Sustainable Transport (2026–2035): Aimed at implementing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) related to transport, including capacity building and global policy.

CAREC Transport Strategy 2030: Aimed at connecting Central Asian countries with sustainable, high-quality infrastructure and improved trade corridors.

The European Commission's mobility strategy: Aims to double high-speed rail and increase public charging points to 3 million by 2030.

Main problems and priorities:

Reducing black carbon and GHG emissions.

Financing major infrastructure projects for connectivity.

Improving the safety, performance-based maintenance, and resilience of existing infrastructure.

Results and Discussion

Today, the modern economy is increasingly integrating from the production sector into the service sector. In this regard, the need for transport infrastructure is very high, as it is an important factor in reducing transportation costs, saving time, and improving the quality of both industrial production and services.

Current global political and economic processes show that countries that possess logistics systems and transport corridors, and are able to use them rationally, are gaining wide-ranging opportunities. In order to evaluate such indicators, the World Bank developed the "Logistics Performance Index" (LPI). This index is an analytical tool that assesses countries' logistics infrastructure, customs efficiency, speed of freight transportation, and quality of services. It measures the ease of movement of goods in international trade and the overall efficiency of the logistics system.

The LPI summarizes countries' performance across six dimensions that reflect important aspects of the logistics environment.

Six main criteria were selected for determining the Logistics Performance Index.

The first part of the LPI survey, consisting of questions 10–15, provides the initial data for the international LPI. Each respondent evaluates eight foreign markets according to the six main components of logistics performance. The eight countries are randomly selected based on the most important export and import markets of the country where the respondent is located. For landlocked countries, neighboring countries that form part of the land bridge connecting them with international markets are selected. The method used to select several countries evaluated by each respondent depends on the characteristics of the country where the respondent is located (Table 1).

Respondents complete the questionnaire online. It includes the random approach of Uniform Sampling in order to obtain the most possible responses from low-income countries [Ministry of Transport of the Republic of Uzbekistan – Open data on logistics performance – <https://mintrans.uz/lpi>].

Since the survey mechanism mainly relies on a special country selection methodology for respondents based on high trade volumes between countries, the random approach of Uniform Sampling can help countries with low trade volumes move to the first position in country selection. After 200 surveys, the random approach of Uniform Sampling is included in the country selection mechanism process. For each new survey respondent, the random approach of Uniform Sampling requests a response from a randomly selected country, but with unequal probability, using selected

weights to convert the selection into a uniform probability. In particular, country i is selected with the probability $(N - ni) / 2N$, where ni is the sample size of country i so far, and N is the total sample size.

Table 1. Criteria for Assessing the Logistics Performance Index

Developed by the author based on World Bank data

Criteria	Characteristics	Importance	Number of questions used in assessment	Weight by LPI components	Rating indicators (1–5)
Customs	Efficiency of customs and other control authorities.	Important for policy-making.	10	0.4	1 – very slow; 2 – low; 3 – medium; 4 – good; 5 – very fast and efficient
Infrastructure	Quality of trade and transport infrastructure, including ports, railways, and roads.	An important indicator for attracting investment in logistics infrastructure.	11	0.42	1 – undeveloped; 2 – unsatisfactory; 3 – average; 4 – good; 5 – highly developed
International shipments	Ease of arranging international shipments at competitive prices.	Helps countries identify and improve gaps in the logistics system.	12	0.4	1 – very expensive and difficult; 2 – difficult; 3 – average; 4 – convenient; 5 – very convenient and inexpensive
Logistics quality	Quality and competence of logistics services, including transport operators and customs brokers.	Countries with well-developed logistics systems have higher competitiveness in international trade.	13	0.42	1 – low; 2 – unsatisfactory; 3 – average; 4 – good; 5 – professional and high-quality

Criteria	Characteristics	Importance	Number of questions used in assessment	Weight by LPI components	Rating indicators (1–5)
Tracking	Ability to track and trace shipments.	Assesses the possibility of using modern IT technologies and artificial intelligence.	14	0.41	1 – not available; 2 – limited; 3 – partial; 4 – close to real time; 5 – full real-time tracking
Timeliness	Arrival of shipments within the scheduled time.	Assesses agreements, trust, and the indicator of being a strategic partner in international trade.	15	0.4	1 – always delayed; 2 – often delayed; 3 – sometimes delayed; 4 – mostly on time; 5 – always on time

The international LPI is a general indicator of the performance of the logistics sector, combining data on six main performance components into a single overall indicator. Some respondents did not provide data for all six components; therefore, interpolation is used to fill in the missing values. Missing values are replaced by the average national value of responses for each question, adjusted according to the respondent’s average deviation from the national average in their answers to the questions.

As can be seen from the table, during the period from 2007 to 2025, logistics performance indicators in Central Asian countries have remained at a relatively low level. At the same time, the average “World” indicator increased from 2.7 to 3.0, which means that logistics systems are steadily developing at the global level.

Based on the diagram, it can be concluded that Kazakhstan’s LPI index increased sharply from 2.1 in 2007 to 2.8 in 2010. In the following years, it stabilized at around 2.7–2.8. This indicates that the country developed its logistics infrastructure relatively quickly.

The Kyrgyz Republic reached 2.6 in 2010, but later a decline was observed, and by 2025 it recovered to 2.5. From the dynamics of this indicator, it can be concluded that the logistics system is not stable and is sensitive to external factors. In other words, there are strong dependencies in foreign policy.

In Tajikistan, there is an overall increase in the LPI index from 1.9 to 2.5. However, across the years, there is a slow but positive development trend.

In Turkmenistan, LPI index data are not complete, but on average they are in the range of 2.2–2.5. The situation is stable, but high growth is not observed. The reason is that a relatively closed political system is observed in this country, and it conducts a policy dependent on the influence of neighboring countries. However, among Central Asian countries, the most convenient

transport infrastructure exists in this territory. The conditions for access to the Caspian Sea, the opportunity to reach large markets through it, and the possibilities of access to the ocean through Pakistan and Iran are higher compared to the remaining countries.

Figure 1. Logistics Performance Index (LPI) by Years
 Developed by the author based on World Bank data

In Uzbekistan, the LPI index reached its highest point in 2010, up to 2.8. However, later it stabilized in the range of 2.4–2.6. In recent years, growth has slowed down, but there has been no decline. For Uzbekistan, access to the ocean is considered a major problem, because reaching sea routes requires passing through two countries. At the same time, in the south, the unstable situation in Afghanistan does not provide a guarantee for security, while Turkmenistan is a closed territory. In the north, there is an opportunity to access the ocean through Kazakhstan and Russia, but since the market where our products can compete has formed in the south, this route is long. Therefore, our opportunity to access the ocean through Russia remains possible only with goods that meet the quality standards of the European Union. In other words, with high-quality goods.

Table 2. Comparative Analysis of the Logistics Performance Index (LPI) of Central Asian Countries, Turkey, and the World in 2007–2025

No.	Countries	2007	2010	2012	2014	2016	2018	2022	2025
1	Kazakhstan	2.1	2.8	2.7	2.7	2.8	2.8	2.7	2.7
2	Kyrgyz Republic	2.4	2.6	2.4	2.2	2.2	2.6	2.3	2.5
3	Tajikistan	1.9	2.4	2.3	2.5	2.1	2.3	2.5	2.5
4	Turkmenistan	—	2.5	—	2.3	2.2	2.4	2.4	2.4
5	Uzbekistan	2.2	2.8	2.5	2.4	2.4	2.6	2.6	2.5
6	Turkey	3.2	3.2	3.5	3.5	3.4	3.2	3.4	3.4
7	World	2.7	2.9	2.9	2.9	2.9			

In Table 2, we analyzed the general LPI index of Turkey and the world in order to conduct a comparative analysis with Central Asian countries. The analysis of Central Asian countries,

including Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, Tajikistan, and the Kyrgyz Republic, was presented above.

The reason we included Turkey in this analysis is that it is ethnically related to Central Asian countries, and it is also interesting because of its geographical location and its policy as a bridge connecting Eurasia. In this regard, Turkey's establishment of a "transport hub" in Istanbul provides the country with advantages in foreign trade, domestic trade, and politics for many years. At the same time, Turkey has the highest indicators, ranging from 3.2 to 3.5. It has a developed logistics system and transport infrastructure, and its result is better than the world average LPI. This indicates that the country has paid more attention and invested more in transport infrastructure than the average level. However, according to the LPI indicator, it is not among the very best countries. For example, in such a table, Singapore ranks first in the world with an LPI index of 4.3, while Finland ranks second with an index of 4.2. Hong Kong is in 10th place among the top 10 with an index of 4.0.

In comparison, Central Asian countries are below the world average level in terms of LPI. The most stable country in the region is Kazakhstan. The countries with the greatest growth potential are Uzbekistan and Tajikistan. In recent years, the strengthening of good-neighborly relations and economic cooperation in the development of these countries' economies has had a positive impact on economic indicators.

These data show the following:

First, logistics infrastructure is still at the stage of development. Many investments and institutional changes need to be introduced into this sector.

Second, transport, the customs system, and the level of digitalization are important factors. Today, all studies on the application of IT in the transport sector show positive correlations.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The analysis conducted above shows that the efficiency of the logistics system is one of the important factors in the economic development of a country. In particular, the speed of customs procedures, the level of development of transport and trade infrastructure, international freight transportation opportunities, the quality of logistics services, cargo tracking systems, and timely delivery are considered the main criteria determining logistics efficiency.

As a result of the analysis, it was identified that these indicators directly determine not only the internal efficiency of the logistics system but also the country's competitiveness in international trade. In particular, the level of use of modern information technologies and artificial intelligence is of great importance in optimizing logistics processes, reducing costs, and improving the quality of services.

At the same time, applying a comprehensive approach in assessing the logistics system, that is, analyzing all criteria on the basis of a single system, makes it possible to compare countries and serves to identify existing problems and develop effective strategies for eliminating them.

In general, sustainable economic growth of the country can be ensured through the development of the logistics system, modernization of infrastructure, acceleration of digitalization processes, and deepening of institutional reforms.

Based on the analysis conducted, in order to increase the efficiency of the logistics system and strengthen its international competitiveness, it is appropriate to put forward the following proposals and recommendations.

First, customs procedures should be further simplified and digitalized. In particular, the wide introduction of electronic declaration systems and the development of risk management systems based on artificial intelligence can reduce the time required for cargo clearance.

Second, the modernization of transport and logistics infrastructure is of great importance. The efficiency of freight transportation can be significantly increased through the development of railways, highways, logistics centers, and warehouse systems.

Third, in order to increase competitiveness in the international freight transportation market, it is necessary to optimize the prices of logistics services and diversify transport routes. This, in turn, will contribute to the expansion of foreign trade volume.

Fourth, in order to improve the quality of logistics services, it is necessary to develop the system of training qualified personnel and improve the professional competencies of transport operators and customs brokers.

Fifth, it is necessary to improve cargo tracking systems and introduce digital platforms that allow real-time monitoring. Through this, the transparency and reliability of logistics processes can be increased.

Sixth, in order to ensure the timely delivery of cargo, it is appropriate to optimize logistics chains, integrate transport and logistics operations, and apply modern management methods.

Seventh, the overall efficiency of the system can be increased by developing cooperation between the state and the private sector in the logistics system, attracting investments, and widely introducing innovative technologies.

In general, the practical implementation of the above recommendations will serve to ensure the sustainable development of the logistics system, expand the volume of foreign trade, and increase the country's competitiveness in the international economic arena.

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